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“MY VOW”

The sunrise color has escaped my notice.
I had not seen such a sky in a year or more.
With the briefest grasp of light, I awaken.
Then there is darkness and my whole world crashes down on me.

Time passes slowly while I drink my coffee.
Bits of life taken in shadowy waterfalls.
I notice my daughter's gentle smile.
I wished she would take after her mother's kind manner.

Every day, the horizon does call.
The sunset is a portal where light does fall.
Deep and encompassing, it whispers of darkness,
Shielding my secret and my suffering.

Vesper is now blooming—a melancholy brightness,
I promise to protect the undertow of the night.
In order to remain awake until the sun rises,
My last fleeting fantasy, my last sunlight.